

A Study of Effectiveness of Online Education in Central Hospitality Institutes of India during Covid-19: Students 'Perspective

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: This is now very much understood that COVID 19 has tremendously impacted all the sectors of society. The field of education among other sectors can still be seen as going through the several phases of changes and research and development in terms of adopting and making teaching and learning effective. The sudden break in traditional method of teaching forced all institutions irrespective of area of study to adopt online teaching without any preparation. The online method of study is now being used by educational institutions without drawing much attention towards its effectiveness. The Students being focal point in education system need to be enquired to analyse their perspective of online mode of study. The study aimed to administer the perspective of students involved in hospitality education in India.

Research methodology: The present study was employed at students of Central Institute of Hotel Management in India. 1557 students participated in the study from across 21 IHMs in India. The data was obtained through self administered questionnaire to collect opinions of students for online mode of study due to pandemic situation.

Results: The study results reveal that students' preference for online mode of study is less motivating but there is a difference in student's perspective for effectiveness for theory and practical. The results also indicate that students give preference to convenience, so far it does not affect the quality of teaching learning process. Overall study results indicate that the students find online study unsatisfactory adopted during covid-19 in the field of hospitality education in India.

Conclusion: Though in this pandemic situation, online study seems to be only effective, approachable and accessible way to conduct classes, yet it needs special attention in context with hospitality education so as to make it equally effective for both of its component i.e. theory and practical input.

Keywords:

effectiveness, Online Education, Students Perspective, Hospitality Institutes

INTRODUCTION

With the COVID-19, a novel Corona Virus disease spread across the landmasses of the Globe, most of the nations need to arrange for the conclusion of scholarly institutions. Educational establishments close themselves refraining physical contacts as they need to prioritize the wellbeing and life of their students from contagious disease which would have spread with a speed, in hefty contact based understudy local area.

The emergency of COVID-19 has a worldwide presence and it is affecting the strength of individuals as well as monetarily, sincerely and socially. Students also are going through issues as Covid - 19 have at last prompted the conclusion of Universities, Colleges Institutes and Schools in India. Various nations have begun mental helpline numbers for the pandemic. In India, National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Sciences (NIMHANS) is providing counselling in 21 states. Guiding is being done on emotional wellness and

psychosocial issues identified with the pandemic Covid-19 through its helpline numbers (The Hindu.com, April 29, 2020).

To forestall loss of study hours online education has been carried out across schools and colleges. Anyway very little time was accessible to prepare academicians and students during the time spent executing the educating learning measures online or setting up prescribed procedures and standard working methods. Online education which was dispatched as a panacea for all infirmities presently needs further introspection. The conclusion of schools and educational offices is the decision of numerous nations, both at the essential and college level all through India. This reality caused alarm at the final assessment. All degrees of educational foundations in India, particularly tertiary establishments feel as one of the organizations affected by the spread of covid-19 unfriendly effects, brought about by students, are needed to take in online from home in view of the end of direct learning face to face in class to break

the chain and openness to the Covid. Moreover, they are not used to plan assignment based learning exercises, when the COVID-19 flare-up, constrained all schools to close and students to gain from home, they faced change issue. To say the least, be that as it may, learning is simply not occurring for a few students. Their speakers need assets to interface in online learning and a lot of students don't approach net affiliation and furthermore the fundamental devices (Lie, 2020).

At that point, learning exercises that were done by the face to face strategy in the classroom/homeroom changed to the online learning framework. The idea of social separating, and physical removing expects everybody to remain at home with the goal that the spread of this infection isn't growing (Deli Allo, 2020). The points of this investigation are students positively have their own perspective on online learning amidst COVID-19 pandemic. Examination to date give insufficient reference in regards to the students' perspective on the online learning led during COVID-19 pandemic. In the interim, the referenced perspective could be a contribution for teachers and foundations to improve online learning quality.

Accordingly, the motivation behind this examination is to research the students' perspective on Online Learning amidst a COVID-19 pandemic.

Objectives

- To analyse the effectiveness of online teaching and learning.
- To assess the impact of online education on learning outcomes for theory and practical subjects.
- To evaluate hospitality student's perspective towards online mode of study.
- To identify factors making learning easier for students through online mode.

Definitions

Perspective

Perspective is an interior interaction which has been perceived by person when chosen and controlled boosts that come from outside. This improvement is caught by one's detects, at that point precipitously singular sentiments and musings will offer importance to the current upgrades (Aw, 2010). Perspective is a perspective on issue that happens or a specific perspective utilized in seeing a phenomenon (Martono, 2010). Perspective Study isn't simply taking a gander at the circumstance, however here students learn, expand their viewpoints, and become another stage to set themselves up later on. In perspective, students can give freedoms to them to expand their viewpoints and perspectives on the universe of work dependent on the encounters of students.

Online Learning

Online learning is education that happens over the net. It's typically said as "e-learning" among different terms. Notwithstanding, on-line learning is just one type of distance learning. As indicated by (Fitriyadi, 2013) shows that some of the expected edges of ICT for education are: working as partner degree enabler for long learning; make changes inside the instructor's job in educating and accordingly the job of researchers in learning; offer open admittance to intelligent material and information through networks; kill time and territory imperatives inside the learning climate; support the association and the executives of learning and education; and open freedoms for cooperation among scholastics and between students. Also, they're acclimated arranging project-based learning exercises.

Effectiveness

'Learning Effectiveness' implies that students who complete an online program get educations that address the particular nature of the organization. The objective is that online learning is in any event identical to learning through the establishment's other conveyance modes, specifically through its conventional face-to-face, classroom based guidance. Communication is vital." Thus learning effectiveness should be the first measure by which online education is judged. On the off chance that we can't learn too online as we can in customary homerooms, at that point online education itself is suspect, and other unmistakably basic issues, like access, understudy and personnel fulfilment, and (might we venture to say it) cost effectiveness are to a great extent superfluous. Without a doubt, when online learning was first considered and executed, a greater part of teachers accepted that it would never be on par with face-to-face learning. Many actually do. Truth be told, notwithstanding, we presently have great and sufficient proof that students by and large learn as much online as they do in customary study hall conditions.

Literature Review:

For long, online education has been seen as a decision that has the capability of serving a specific gathering of students that are quite more seasoned and bear more natural, financial, and business related duties contrasted with nearby students (Jung Rhea, 2000; Hussein, Daoud, Alrabaiah, Owais, 2020). This is especially evident on the grounds that numerous teachers and students who had never had sufficient (assuming any) insight with online learning wound up obliged to do as such with negligible support. However this action has demonstrated to be quite possibly the most profoundly effective non-drug mediations forced by governments in containing the spread of the sickness (Flaxman, 2020a; Moosa, 2020), it has likewise put each one of those engaged with the educational interaction under

generous pressure. In numerous cases, the after-effect of crisis online learning was a considerable trade off to the nature of the learning experience (DeVaney, Shimshon, Rascoff, Maggioncalda, 2020; Hodges, Moore, Locke, Trust, Bond, 2020).

Nonetheless, given the suddenness of the matter and the difficulty and vulnerability of the circumstance, it is justifiable that all gatherings associated with the educational cycle would be excusing and tolerating of a not exactly amazing presentation, particularly during the first wave of the pandemic.

As indicated by Asabere (2012), online learning intends to look for changes in the example of entire scholastic interaction. Online learning is known with numerous names and terms like learning through web, online learning, guidance through computer help. Online learning has numerous definitions in the specific situations and milieu of its operationalization.

As indicated by Berteau (2009), a few experts were of the thought that online learning is a method of instructing in which various mix of innovation are looked for while some were of the ideas that it is substitute of distance education, which is worked with by the utilization of web considered as an effective method of quick interchanges. Nichols (2003: 01) expressed that online learning is a bunch of mix of different kinds of innovations exclusively to advance education. Online learning is an expansive term, which gives total depiction of different sorts of online learning receiving the cutting edge Information and Communication Technologies (ICT).

A few investigations demonstrated that online learning and their appropriation was generally affected by students' attributes, which were viewed as significant elements in online learning in agricultural nations (Bhuasiri et.al. 2012). These qualities comprise self-efficacy of web, and involvement with computer and web, uneasiness with computer ease of use and ways to deal with online learning (Chu & Chu 2010). Students' mentalities are likewise affected through the greatness and effectiveness of utilizing course of online learning, convenience of online learning, and students' level and abilities in computer (Aixia & Wang, 2011). Their computer encounters, which comprise evident self use, gratification and viability and use of online learning assume a predominant part (Liaw, 2011). All things considered, uplifting perspectives of students' and practices in regards to online learning are significant and essential towards the acknowledgment and appropriation of online learning (Selim, 2007). The negative perspectives of students towards online learning were additionally found in some past research contemplates. The negative mentalities of students towards online learning were identified with low degree of computer abilities, innovative nervousness, and computer equipment issues, just as helpless investigation abilities, low inspiration, and a failure to

work freely (Smith, et.al.2000, Govindasamy, 2001; Rosenberg, 2001). Another adverse factor in regards to online learning was that online classes need individual contact with the educator and friends. A few examinations consider detailed that a few students had sensations of separation and dejection when they were needed to face a computer screen.

Quality of higher education: Quality of higher education can be defined in multiple ways. Longacker and Blanco (2003) defined it as by who and how students are taught rather than by what students learn. Their definition highlights both the perspectives of academic staff and administrators. Later, Koslowski (2006) defined both of these perspectives separately. Following the competition-based view, dimensions of higher education quality are expressed by quality of students, faculty credentials, academic features, and administrative supports (Akareem Hossain, 2012; Ashraf et al., 2009).

First, students' qualification and their background, according to Akareem and Hossain (2012), contribute significantly to defining the quality of education. Second, qualifications of teaching staff are found to be one of the most important factors affecting the perception of education quality. Arnon and Reichel (2007) showed that students see two types of images of teachers: the image of an ideal teacher and own self-image as a teacher.

Third, an important aspect of education quality is identified by academic factors within the universities. Lizzio et al. (2002) explored that perception about university learning Environment contributes to academic outcome, whereas it is not influenced by prior academic achievements.

Lastly, the administration systems of a university will also determine how well a projected plan will be implemented to ensure the quality of education. In their research, Nadiri, Kandampully, and Hussain (2009) tried to examine the perceived service quality provided by the administrative units, for example, services provided by the registrar, library, faculty office, rector office, dormitory, sports, and health care center. All of these four dimensions determine the quality of higher education (Akareem Hossain, 2012; Ashraf et al., 2009). However, extant literature does not clearly identify which characteristics make the students of Hospitality Education perceive these dimensions differently. Therefore, this study takes a quantitative research approach to identify this research gap.

Students Perception of Online Learning:

It may be also be concluded that students have no positive attitude regarding online learning at undergraduate level due to high difficulty level in understanding and using online learning programme without having appropriate guidance, however the

computer mediated instruction are useful for students' course work (Obaid Ullah, 2017). Teachers and students suggested continuous faculty development. They recommended a reduction in cognitive load and increased interactivities during online teaching (Mukhtar K, Javed K, Arooj M, Sethi A.2020). In their study of students perception and attitudes towards online learning T Muthuprasad et al. (2021) are of the opinion that Majority of students evinced a positive attitude towards online classes in the wake of corona.

Research Methodology

The present study was aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of online education in the field of hospitality education in India. Therefore the researchers chose the students enrolled / studying with Central institutes of Hotel Management in India to conduct the study. Currently there are 21 central institutes providing education in the field of hospitality across India. The population for the study was all the three years students who are enrolled in B.Sc. in Hospitality and Hotel Administration course in these central IHMs. The study consisted of self administered questionnaire containing questions based of demographic profile and followed by

attributes to evaluate the efficacy of online education for theory and practical separately. The data was collected online through Google forms questionnaire. To collect responses from students, principals /faculty members of each institute were shared with the link to further forward it to students. The data was collected in a span of two weeks from 17th to 29th January 2021. Total 1592 students responded to the questionnaire from all 21 institutes, out of which 1557 usable responses were analysed to conduct the study. The SPSS (version 26) was used and the descriptive statistics (frequency, mean analysis) were computed to analyse the data.

Analysis and Results

Demographic Profile

The table 1.0 displays the respondents' demographic details in terms of their gender and age. It is clear from the table that 75.6 % male students and 24.4 % female students have participated in the study. The table also signifies that maximum 65.5% students were from 16-20 years age followed by 33.7 % from 21-24 years of age group.

Table 1.0 Demographic Profile

Students profile	(N= 1557)	nos.	percentage
Gender	Female	380	24.4 %
	Male	1177	75.6 %
Age	16-20	1020	65.5 %
	21-24	525	33.7 %
	25-28	12	0.8 %
Total		1557	100 %

Table 1.1 elaborates on the strength of student's participation enrolled in different years of B.Sc. in H&HA course. The table shows that 1st year students

with 51.3% have maximum participation followed by 3rd year (32.3 %) and 2nd year (16.4 %) students.

Table 1.1 Student's year of study

Student's year of study	nos.	percentage	
Course	B.Sc. 1 st year	799	51.3 %
	B.Sc. 2 nd year	255	16.4 %
	B.Sc. 3 rd year	503	32.3 %
Total		1557	100 %

Table 1.2 describes the number of student respondents from each institute across India. The maximum student participation had been from IHM Luknow (22.2%)

followed by IHM Bhopal (13.3%), IHM Jaipur (12.1%) and AIHM Chandigarh (9.0%).

Table 1.2 Respondents percentage from each CIHM.

Institute	nos.	percentage
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AIHM Chandigarh	140	9.0 %
IHM Bangalore	30	1.9 %
IHM Bhopal	207	13.3 %
IHM Bhubaneswar	3	0.2 %
IHM Chennai	44	2.8 %
IHM Gandhinagar	18	1.2 %
IHM Goa	95	6.1 %
IHM Gurdaspur	50	3.2 %
IHM Guwahati	36	2.3 %
IHM Gwalior	129	8.3 %
IHM Hajipur	24	1.5 %
IHM Hyderabad	4	0.3 %
IHM Jaipur	189	12.1 %
IHM Kolkata	38	2.4 %
IHM Lucknow	345	22.2 %
IHM Mumbai	9	0.6 %
IHM Pusa, Delhi	70	4.5 %
IHM Shillong	42	2.7 %
IHM Shimla	2	0.1 %
IHM Shrinagar	68	4.4 %
IHM Thiruvananthapuram	14	0.9 %
Total	1557	100.0

Table 1.3 explains that most of the students (70%) used their mobile phones to connect with online classes Whereas laptop/desktop have also been used but found

to be less preferred device to connect to the online classes as compare to mobile phones.

Table 1.3 Device used by students to attend online class

Device used by students to attend online class	nos.	percentage
Mobile phone	1090	70 %
Laptop / Desktop	132	8.5 %
Tablet	15	1 %
Mobile phone, Laptop/Desktop	318	20.4 %
All three	2	0.1 %
Total	1557	100 %

Table 1.4 defines that Mobile network had been majorly used (74.8 %) as source to avail internet facility followed by broadband for attending online classes.

This indicates the need of strong internet connectivity to facilitate the learning through mobile network across India.

Table 1.4 Source of Internet access

Source of Internet access	nos.	percentage
Mobile Network	1164	74.8 %
Broadband	238	15.35 %
Mobile Network / Broadband	155	10 %
Total	1557	100 %

Table 1.5 shows the preferences of online video conferencing platforms by the institutes to conduct online classes. Google meet (58.3 %), Cisco Webex

(15.9 %), Zoom (13.9 %), Microsoft teams (10.8 %) and Wise app (1.1 %) online platforms were used by the institutes to convene online classes respectively.

Table 1.5 Online video conferencing platform used by Institutes to conduct classes

Online platform used by Institutes to conduct classes	nos.	percentage
Google meet	908	58.3 %
Zoom	216	13.9 %
Microsoft teams	168	10.8 %
Cisco Webex	248	15.9 %
Wise app	17	1.1 %
Total	1557	100 %

Table 1.6 is an attempt to understand the choice of students for mode of exam after the college reopens and students begin with their study in institute premises. The data reveals that 80.5 % students have given preference

Table 1.6 Students preference for mode of exam for future examinations

Preference for mode of exam	nos.	percentage
MCQ (Online)	1253	80.5 %
Descriptive (Offline)	304	19.5 %
Total	1557	100 %

to online MCQ pattern for holding future examinations as compare to 16.5 % students who have shown their interest in offline traditional mode of examination.

Table 2.0 to table 2.2 exhibits the student’s perspective for effectiveness of theoretical classes conducted through online mode.

Table 2.0 explains the impact of different teaching aids (ppt, video lectures, jam board and audio) used for conducting online theory classes. To evaluate the effectiveness of each teaching aid the aggregate of

Table 2.0 Student’s perspective on effectiveness of teaching aids

Online teaching aids	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total	Mean	Std. Dev.
PPT sharing	13.9	12.3	26.27	23.3	33.7	16.7	50.42	3.27	1.271
Video lectures	16.0	17.0	33.01	20.9	31.9	14.2	46.05	3.11	1.298
Live Jam board demonstration	16.6	17.4	33.98	30.8	24.4	10.9	35.26	2.96	1.230
Audio lecture	20.7	20.2	40.98	22.4	26.9	9.8	36.67	2.85	1.292

Table 2.1 demonstrates the student’s perspective for effectiveness of teaching attributes. . To evaluate the effectiveness of each teaching attribute, the aggregate of ‘strongly disagree’, ‘disagree’ responses and ‘agree’, ‘strongly agree’ responses have been summed up. The students have given higher appreciation to attribute

Table 2.1 Student’s perspective on effectiveness of teaching attributes

Teaching attributes	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Neither agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total	Mean	Std. Dev.
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‘handout availability and clarity’ (46.18 %), followed by ‘ease in assignment’ (44.12 %) and ‘ease in time management’ (40.98%). Whereas ‘feel of classroom activity’ and ‘ease of availing missed lectures’ attributes found to have lowest percentage for effectiveness through online mode.

	nor disagree								
Lecture content and clarity through online mode	18.8	20.1	38.92	26.9	24.9	9.3	34.17	2.86	1.247
Handout availability and clarity through online mode	13.9	16.4	30.38	23.4	31.3	14.9	46.18	3.17	1.266
Effective session interaction	16.7	19.2	35.90	25.3	27.9	10.9	38.79	2.97	1.254
Easy in time management	19.3	16.3	35.58	23.4	27.3	13.7	40.98	3.00	1.325
Active Participation	18.6	17.1	35.71	25.1	27.7	11.5	39.18	2.96	1.285
Ease of Communication	19.7	17.6	37.25	23.4	26.7	12.6	39.31	2.95	1.316
Ease of Assignment	17.6	16.8	34.36	21.5	29.8	14.3	44.12	3.06	1.319
Feel of Classroom activity	33.6	21.5	55.11	21.3	16.3	7.3	23.64	2.42	1.297
Ease of availing Missed lectures	25.9	22.9	48.81	24.3	19.2	7.6	26.85	2.60	1.266
Online sessions are economical.	20.4	17.2	37.57	26.3	24.9	11.2	36.10	2.89	1.294

Table 2.2 reveals overall perspective of students towards the impact of online study for theory subjects. It is clear from the data that 27.36 percent students find learning outcome better through online mode for

studying theory subjects whereas 51.25 percent students have shown disagreement with the statement. Although 21.4 percent students like to remain neutral in response to overall effectiveness of online study.

Table 2.2 Student’s perspective for effectiveness of online theoretical teaching and learning

Overall (Teaching aid + attributes)	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total	Mean	Std. Dev.
Overall learning outcome for theory is more effective through online class method	31.5	19.7	51.25	21.4	17.3	10.0	27.36	2.55	1.352

Table 3.0 to table 3.2 exhibits the student’s perspective for effectiveness of Practical classes conducted through online mode.

Table 3.0 explains the impact of different teaching aids (ppt, video lectures, jam board and audio) used for conducting online practical classes. To evaluate the effectiveness of each teaching aid the aggregate of ‘strongly disagree’, ‘disagree’ responses and ‘agree’, ‘strongly agree’ responses have been combined. The

analyses of student’s responses reveal that ‘live demonstration’ has been the most effective medium to transfer skill orientation through online platform followed by video lectures (you tube videos or self made videos), ppt sharing and audio lectures. Though students have given higher positive response to attribute ‘live demonstration’ but for all the attributes disagreement scores are higher as compare to agreement scores. This signifies that students are highly dissatisfied with practical classes conducted through online mode.

Table 3.0 Student’s perspective on effectiveness of teaching aids

Online practical teaching aids	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total	Mean	Std. dev.
PPT sharing	31.0	23.4	54.40	20.4	17.4	7.8	25.18	2.48	1.298
Video lectures	29.7	22.0	51.70	19.4	19.8	9.1	28.90	2.57	1.334
Live demonstration	26.7	19.7	46.31	23.9	19.0	10.8	29.80	2.68	1.334
Audio lecture	30.7	23.7	54.40	22.7	16.6	6.4	22.93	2.44	1.255

Table 3.1 demonstrates the student’s perspective for effectiveness of teaching attributes. To evaluate the effectiveness of each teaching attribute, the aggregate of ‘strongly disagree’, ‘disagree’ responses and ‘agree’, ‘strongly agree’ responses have been summed up. The students have shown higher disagreements scores for each practical attribute as compare to agreement scores.

This indicates low perception of students for teaching attributes effectiveness of practical classes delivered through online mode.

Although attributes ‘ease of communication’ with 30.38 % and ‘active participation’ with 25.88 % found to have highest percentage among all the attributes.

Table 3.1 Student’s perspective for effectiveness of online practical teaching and learning

Practical teaching attributes	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total	Mean	Std. dev.
Practical content and clarity through online mode	30.3	24.5	54.72	24.7	15.0	5.7	20.62	2.41	1.219
Effective practical session interaction	29.5	24.7	54.21	23.1	16.8	5.8	22.67	2.45	1.235
Active Participation	28.2	20.0	48.23	25.9	19.0	6.9	25.88	2.56	1.266
Ease of Communication	25.8	19.2	44.96	24.7	22.5	7.9	30.38	2.68	1.288
Feel of Practical lab activity	44.2	23.6	67.76	16.6	9.8	5.8	15.61	2.10	1.232

Table 3.2 reveals overall perspective of students towards the impact of online practical subjects. The results reveal that students have overall higher dissatisfaction with online mode of practical classes. The data describes that 64.03 percent students had

shown disagreement for learning outcome whereas only 16.63 % students found online mode effective for practical classes as compare to traditional method. Although 19.3 percent students like to remain neutral in response to overall effectiveness of online study.

Table 3.2 Student’s perspective for effectiveness of online practical teaching and learning

Overall (Teaching aid + attributes)	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total	Mean	Std. dev.
Overall learning outcome is more effective for practical through online class method	42.0	22.0	64.03	19.3	10.6	6.0	16.63	2.17	1.247

Table 4.0 presents the comparative overview for effectiveness of overall theory and practical learning

outcome. The comparative evaluation throws light on the students overall perspective for learning outcomes for both theory and practical subjects. The results for

overall comparison signify that students found online mode of study less effective for both (theory and practical). The table describes 68.97 % students registered disagreement for theory and 64.03 % for

practical. Although higher agreement scores (27.36 %) were recorded for theory subjects which implies that students preferred online theory over practical classes.

Table 4.0 Comparative overview of effectiveness of overall online theory and practical learning outcome

Overall (Teaching aid + attributes)	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Overall learning outcome for theory is more effective through online class method	31.5	19.7	68.97	21.4	17.3	10.0	27.36
Overall learning outcome is more effective for practical through online class method	42.0	22.0	64.03	19.3	10.6	6.0	16.63

Conclusion

The study results present the views of students studying in Central Institutes of Hospitality Education in India. The results provide several factors to improve effectiveness of practical and theory learning through online mode. The analyses of data reveal that students’ preference for online mode of study is less motivating but there is a difference in student’s perspective for effectiveness for theory and practical. Although few factors such as handout availability and clarity, ease in assignment, and ease in time management present positive picture in terms conducting theory classes in online mode. Whereas practical classes conducted in online mode through different teaching aids do not seem to produce effective learning outcome for students. The results also indicate that students give preference to convenience, so far it does not affect the quality of teaching learning process. Some of the lowest scored items were ‘feel of class’ and ‘ease of availing missed lectures’ for theory subject and ‘feel of practical lab’, ‘practical content and clarity’ and ‘effective session interaction for practical classes’ conducted in online mode. Thus the overall study results indicate that the students find online study unsatisfactory adopted during covid-19 in the field of hospitality education in India. Although certain teaching aids and attributes had been appreciated by the large number of students express that these online practices may be included while conducting face to face classes.

In light of the after effects of the exploration above, in spite of the difficulties that they face, it tends to be presumed that the understudies have both positive and negative point of view on internet learning amidst COVID-19 pandemic. They believe web based figuring out how to be exceptionally useful, albeit not completely proficient, amidst a pandemic. The presence of a few hindrances in the execution of web based learning is relied upon to be an assessment later on with the goal that it is consistently prepared when confronted circumstance like this. In view of the viewpoint of

understudies in this examination identified with web based learning amidst COVID-19 pandemic, government, instructors and school ought to do endeavours to oblige understudies’ condition, for example, absence of monetary help and web access accessibility.

E-learning is by all accounts the impending pattern. It has been broadening far reaching. The online technique for learning seems appropriate to everyone during this pandemic situation. Contingent upon their accessibility and resources, students across the globe adopt learning through online platform in this helpful time. This empowers the student to acquire knowledge at whatever point they need it. The discoveries of the examination mirror the effect of E-learning in terms of utilizing E-learning assets, and their presentation. All in all, this examination showed that E-learning has gotten very mainstream and promising method in the world especially during the lockdown time frame because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Though in this pandemic situation, online study seems to be the only effective, approachable and accessible way to conduct classes, yet it needs special attention in context with hospitality education so as to make it equally effective for both of its component i.e. theory and practical input.

Limitations

The study aimed to understand the effectiveness of online education from the perspective of students enrolled with CIHMs in India. Thus it provides the overview of students studying in these institutes only and insufficient to summarize overall perspective of students enrolled with similar courses in other institutes and universities in India.

Future studies

Future studies may widen the horizon of study by considering teacher’s perspective along with student’s perspective and include the students enrolled with other Hospitality institutes across India to understand and

evaluate the effectiveness of learning through online mode due to the pandemic COVID -19.

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